

EXPERIENCES WITH NEW STEAM SOURCE INTEGRATION INTO A REFINERY'S STEAM NETWORK

Variny M.^{1,2}, Illés P.³, Hanus K.¹, Šupa I.¹, Mierka O.^{1,2}

¹*Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovak republic*

²*GRUCON s.r.o., Nezábudková 24, 821 01 Bratislava, Slovak republic*

³*SLOVNAFT, a.s., Vlčie hrdlo 1, 824 12 Bratislava, Slovak republic*
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk

Abstract

Operation of the steam network in a common refinery is influenced by a number of factors, some of them being of seasonal nature, whereas others gain or lose importance along the development of the refinery itself. These factors are likely to escalate on the low pressure steam level (around 4 to 6 bar pressure typically). Several reasons for such state exist: Firstly this steam is used for space heating and steam tracking and may even be exported to a nearby town for residential heating if such possibility exists – all of this leading to extensive seasonal dependence of its consumption. Secondly a lot of such steam is generated in local steam sources in the production units themselves and is exhausted from steam drives if present. All this may lead to a state that a common refinery produces nearly all low pressure steam it consumes in summer, leaving little space left for low pressure steam saving projects and possibly decreasing their NPV. The same holds true for waste heat utilization projects for low pressure steam generation. Under such circumstances an efficient integration of a new local low pressure steam source into existing low pressure steam network and its balance is quite a challenge.

Our contribution deals with preparations undertaken to incorporate a new steam source producing typically 30-40 t/h of nearly saturated low pressure steam into low pressure steam balance. Two alternatives for its quality upgrade were considered in the past, each leading to different impacts on refinery's steam and electricity balance. Taking a look back, with the help of design and operational data, the marginal effect of the realized alternative compared to the other one is evaluated.

Introduction

Steam production in petroleum and refining industry as well as in other energy intense industries contributes a lot to fuel energy consumption. In the US petroleum and refining industry its corresponding share in the process end use of energy is between 20 and 30 %^{1,2}. Optimization of steam production, steam network design and its end use is continuous subject of many scientific energy studies, implementing pinch analysis and site integration approach³, load scheduling⁴ or generally some dedicated mathematical modelling⁵⁻⁸ but also many governmental reports and other studies⁹ formulating simple "golden rules" and guidelines to be followed¹⁰.

Considering production and consumption of low pressure steam, a solution containing a thermocompressor is widely applied to recover steam at lower pressure and supply it to higher pressure steam main¹¹. It does not use any mechanic or electric energy to perform this task, since it uses the motive steam as source of pressure energy. Its performance thus strongly depends on the pressure ratios between motive, exhaust and suction steam, on pressure losses related to thermocompressor incorporation in the steam pipeline as well as on actual suction steam mass flow. In case the low pressure steam is obtained by steam throttling of high pressure steam, thermocompressor installation does not affect electric balance of the industry. However if a large industry equipped by cogeneration unit is considered, high pressure steam usage as motive steam for a thermocompressor to produce low or middle pressure steam results in lowering electric output of this unit. Therefore the impact of this proven and cheap solution on both fuel and electricity balance of the industry needs to be examined carefully.

In this study we present the results of incorporation of a new steam source into existing refinery's steam network balance with respect to two different options to perform the necessary upgrade the produced nearly saturated steam before being exported to the grid:

- simultaneous pressure and temperature increase in a thermocompressor
- superheat in a separate heat exchanger

The alternative that has been put into reality exhibits, compared to other one, substantial improvement in backpressure electric energy production in the central steam and power plant (CSPP) accompanied by overall steam saving, resulting in fuel saving in the CSPP.

System description

New plastics production line releases substantial amounts of middle to low potential heat that by its design is converted to nearly saturated low pressure steam (LPS) in steam generators. Therefore, before being sent to refinery's low pressure steam network, its quality needs to be upgraded.

Steam from Central steam and power plant (CSPP) is supplied to the refinery on three pressure levels – as high pressure steam (HPS, appr. 3.5 MPa), medium pressure steam (MPS, appr. 1.1 MPa) and LPS at around 0.5 MPa. All three steams are superheated by at least 50 to 100 (LPS) to over 100 (MPS, HPS) °C. Under normal circumstances steam on all three pressure levels is produced in backpressure or extraction-condensing steam turbines located in the CSPP from fresh steam (over 8.5 MPa/520 °C) produced in the boilers.

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of the system under study and possible solutions of steam quality upgrade leading to different changes in steam export to refinery and internal power production

High and intermediate pressure steam export from CSPP is less dependent on the actual season of the year, it rather follows the amount of crude processed. On the contrary, LPS supply from the CSPP depends much on the season; it varies between 10 to 30 t/h in summer to over 140 t/h in winter. Apart from steam quality issues on high and intermediate pressure level which are not subject of this analysis, there are quality issues with low pressure steam mainly in summer, due to low steam velocity in main steam pipelines. Many production units in the refinery are self sufficient regarding the LPS or even export part of it. Thus steam cools down and starts condensing in several parts of the main LPS pipelines before it is consumed. Wet steam transport causes often breakdown of condensate traps which leads to steam losses through steam traps bypasses and increases the expenses for their repair or replacement. Experiences of steam network operators show, that minimum acceptable LPS export from the CSPP to prevent serious LPS network operational problems is 10 t/h. Operational states that would lead to lower or even zero LPS export from the CSPP have to be solved by excess steam venting to the atmosphere. It must be stressed that a lot of work has been done in the past to reduce the LPS excess in summer preventing such situation to become daily's routine in summer months.

The above situation defined the frame for decision-making process about the means of LPS produced in the new production unit upgrade. Concise depiction of the balanced system layout and two selected possible solutions can be found in Figure 1.

Solution "A" appeared first and has been preferred for some time due to anticipated low investment cost and its quite wide use in industry¹¹. Two thermocompressors should be installed in "A" case, with different suction capacities, to cope with changeable LPS production according to production unit load. HPS from CSPP should serve as motive steam in the thermocompressors, raising the temperature of the LPS by more than 50 °C and pressure by around 1 bar (at thermocompressor flanges). This means the consumed HPS would become part of the LPS exported from the thermocompressors to the refinery. Design calculations stated that for 40 t/h of LPS upgraded, nearly 20 t/h of motive steam should be needed, leading up to 60 t/h LPS export from the thermocompressors. It became obvious that such amount of LPS cannot be utilized efficiently in the refinery during summer. Moreover, the associated decrease in backpressure electric energy production in the CSPP would lead to extra electric energy purchase costs.

Solution "B" appeared firstly as unfeasible, since doubts were expressed if the produced steam temperature could be raised to sufficient level with condensing HPS (condensing temperature around 240 °C) and if the pressure losses in the heat exchanger would limit the steam export to the refinery. The fact that such solution

was novel in the refinery at that time also contributed to this situation. A later successful application of a similar solution on a smaller scale in another production unit served as good example and the final superheated design allowed to achieve LPS temperatures over 220 °C with acceptable pressure losses. This solution offers several advantages compared to the “A” solution. Namely, the HPS consumed in the steam quality upgrade process does not become part of the LPS, thus the LPS export to the refinery is lower than in the “A” case and the probability of its complete utilization in the refinery is thus higher. Secondly, HPS consumption is much smaller in this case, leading to higher backpressure power production in the CSPP compared to the “A” case.

At the time of decision-making other system parts already were installed. As found out the pipeline for LPS export to the refinery has limited capacity and assuming the upper limit steam flow velocity of 40 m/s (both confirmed by steam pipeline operators and available literature¹²) yielded maximum 50 t/h LPS export capacity even for the “A” case that should produce steam with higher pressure than “B”. Due to its length (appr. 1 km) its replacement by a bigger one is not to be thought of. This means that even in winter when over 100 t/h LPS are consumed in the refinery, LPS export capacity is limited by existing pipeline. If case “B” was to be realized, this fact would limit the thermocompressors operation causing part of the produced nearly saturated steam to be sent to air condensers (see Figure 1).

All those facts contributed to the final decision to realize the alternative “B” as the preferred solution for existing situation. The steam superheater has been set into operation in 2017 and positive references about its reliable operation spread in the whole refinery. Evaluation process required to define proper steam and electricity saving calculation scheme by which the benefit of the “B” alternative over the “A” one could be estimated from process data. It is based on:

- measured export of LPS from the steam superheated and from the CSPP
- measured consumption of the HPS in the steam superheater
- verified marginal backpressure electricity production in the CSPP considering steam expansion from HP to LP level
- thermocompressors operation characteristics (motive steam consumption as the function of exported LPS from the thermocompressors)
- HPS and LPS balance calculations yielding maximum mass flows of motive and suction steam in the “A” case with respect to export pipeline capacity (max. 50 t/h) and with respect to limitation of minimum LPS export from CSPP (10 t/h)

Results and discussion

We selected August 2017 as a representative summer month for analyses. The measured LPS export from both CSPP and superheater during the selected time period is shown in Figure 2. The LPS export from CSPP varies between 10 and 50 t/h and shows correlation with LPS export from superheater, especially in the second half of the month. As the new production unit operates in ON/OFF mode, so does also behave the export from the preheater. The LPS export from preheater impact on CSPP operation can be in some cases counterbalanced by steam drives switching to electrodrives in the refinery, as reported in an earlier conference paper¹³. Most of the time however we see that the export of LPS from CSPP is low which limits the export from preheater – it has been confirmed by the plant operators that part of the produced nearly saturated steam is led to air condenser, meaning that only 20 to 30 t/h steam is exported from preheater compared to typical available LPS amount of 30 to 45 t/h (see a short period between 18.8. and 23.8. when more than 40 t/h LPS has been exported from the preheater).

Results of calculations shown in Figure 3 rely to the above findings. In case the thermocompressors would be installed, they would produce typically 30 to 50 t/h LPS, being limited mostly with required minimum LPS export from CSPP and only rarely by steam pipeline capacity (50 t/h). The difference between thick grey and thin black data represents steam saving due to realisation of “B” compared to “A”. As can be seen it is typically between 0 and 5 t/h, rarely above. Similar trends can be seen in other summer months. Calculated motive HPS flows during stable operation vary between 10 and 16 t/h (difference between thick black and thin black data).

Figure 2. Low pressure steam export from the CSPP and from the steam superheater in selected time period

Figure 3. Visualization of measured LPS export from superheater versus calculated LPS suction to thermocompressors and export from thermocompressors in selected time period

All these findings allow the cumulative final steam saving and produced backpressure electricity increase estimation – it amounts to over 1000 ton of steam and over 500 MWh of electricity in August 2017.

Conclusions

Standard refineries are nearly self-sufficient in terms of low pressure steam production and consumption in summer, which makes the incorporation of a new low pressure steam source under such circumstances difficult. As demonstrated in our contribution, proper evaluation of underlying alternatives leading to this goal is vital for sound project economics and success. Traditional solutions may not be the most effective ones and sometimes a novel approach should be considered and tested. Though the selected and realized solution still does not lead to full utilization of available steam in summer, it performs better than the traditional solution would and helps also to produce more backpressure electric energy in the CSPP. Further projects for available low pressure steam production capacity utilization from the new production unit are in progress in adjacent units with the ambition to minimize steam losses in summer and to help a stable low pressure steam network operation.

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